

Abstract ID: P-22

Title: AutoData Steward: An AI-Driven Framework for FAIR-Compliant Data Lifecycle Optimization in HPC Environments

Authors and Presenter: **Muhammad Umair Meo** | Technische Universität Chemnitz

The exponential growth of datasets produced by simulations, artificial intelligence (AI), and interdisciplinary research within high-performance computing (HPC) systems has amplified the demand for intelligent, scalable, and FAIR-compliant data management solutions. Traditional approaches—such as manual file tiering, static allocation rules, and inadequate metadata handling—struggle to meet the dynamic requirements of modern scientific workflows, particularly in distributed and collaborative environments. These limitations not only hinder reproducibility and data reuse but also drive up infrastructure costs and impede scientific progress.

To address these challenges, this paper presents AutoData Steward: FAIR and Storage Optimization Toolkit, an AI-driven, modular prototype designed to automate data lifecycle management while promoting transparency, scalability, and reusability. The system passively monitors file system activity, classifies datasets into active or inactive categories, enriches metadata using natural language processing (NLP), and evaluates FAIR compliance through structured scoring mechanisms. A lightweight back end based on SQLite and JSON ensures portability, while a Flask-based dashboard provides visual insights into storage utilization, metadata quality, and compliance recommendations.

Key components of the prototype include: (i) a data usage monitor leveraging Python watchdog and shell scripts, (ii) a metadata enrichment module powered by spaCy, (iii) a FAIR assessment engine offering compliance scores, and (iv) an intuitive dashboard for researchers and administrators. Initial evaluations using synthetic datasets demonstrate that AutoData Steward improves data visibility, reduces redundant storage, and enhances compliance with FAIR principles. By aligning with reproducible research standards, this toolkit supports sustainable data stewardship and efficient storage management in HPC environments.